

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

Deliverable 5.3

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Abbreviations list

DMP	Data Management Plan
DMP-IF	Data Management Plan Interoperability Framework
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAIR-IF	FAIR Testing Interoperability Framework
LMS	Learning Management System
maDMP	Machine actionable Data Management Plan
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SGK	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework

Executive Summary

The OSTrails project aims to facilitate the adoption of a FAIR-by-design culture within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), and Research Infrastructure (RI) providers. A key component of this effort is a structured training and support strategy that leverages a multi-channel learning approach to empower researchers, trainers, and specialists in Open Science, Research Data Management (RDM), and FAIR data practices. The training strategy follows a dual approach: a) Business-to-Business (B2B): Focused on equipping trainers and specialists with the knowledge to support research institutions and funding bodies; b) Business-to-Consumer (B2C): Targeting researchers from national and European research infrastructures through pilot training programs.

OSTrails' training roadmap is designed to build a sustainable training ecosystem by developing a network of trainers and strengthening competence centres at the European, national, and infrastructure levels. This ensures long-term capacity building and knowledge dissemination. The roadmap key training initiatives include:

- A training library with guidance toolkits, tutorials, and case studies
- Online courses and e-learning platforms such as OpenAIRE's OpenPlato¹ and INRIA's ePoc²
- Train-the-trainer bootcamps and a mentorship programme
- A trainer network and directory for knowledge-sharing

Additionally, OSTrails plays a pivotal role in fostering collaboration among research communities, competence centres, and policy makers. While it does not create a competence centre itself, it serves as an enabler, providing tools, expertise, and frameworks to advance Open Science practices. The roadmap ensures all learning resources are openly accessible, promoting scalability and impact.

D5.3 is structured into five chapters, covering the training roadmap, learning platforms, methodologies, competence centre integration, and a timeline of key training activities. The report underscores the importance of structured training in developing a connected and sustainable research ecosystem across Europe.

¹ OpenPlato: <https://openplato.eu/>

² ePoc: <https://epoc.inria.fr/en/>

1. Introduction

OSTrails can play a pivotal role in helping RPOs, RFOs, and RI providers adopt a FAIR-by-design culture, with training and support activities serving as key enablers through the implementation of a multi-channel learning strategy.

The primary **goal of the training and support strategy in OSTrails** is to boost knowledge and skills through a dual approach—Business-to-Business (B2B) for trainers and specialists and Business-to-Consumer (B2C) for researchers. By implementing a structured training programme presented in this roadmap, OSTrails effort aims to empower specialists and trainers within research institutions, funding bodies, and RIs, mainly in the second year of the project, and in the third year, further extend to train researchers from national or European research infrastructures, leveraging pilot programmes to ensure hands-on learning experiences.

The **training strategy** focuses on two key objectives: developing a structured training ecosystem to deliver specialised training and cultivate a network of trainers, while simultaneously strengthening and expanding established competence centres at European, national, and infrastructure levels to ensure long-term sustainability and capacity building.

The **training roadmap** outlines key initiatives and resources designed to achieve OSTrails training objectives. These include a training library, learning resources and guidance toolkits, online courses, train-the-trainer bootcamps, a mentorship programme, and a trainer network and directory. In this deliverable the roadmap is organised by training activities and learning resources, detailing their purpose, target audience, learning objectives, timeline, and milestones.

Figure 1. OSTrails Training Roadmap: Key Initiatives and Resources.

The **integrated competence** centre’s purpose is focused on the OSTrails aim to support the development and enhancement of Open Science, RDM and FAIR data competence centres at European, national, and infrastructure levels by fostering collaboration, best practices sharing, and alignment with initiatives within the EOSC ecosystem producing relevant learning resources, like Skills4EOSC and others mentioned in the “FAIR Implementation Framework”³. While it does not establish a competence centre itself, it serves as a key enabler, providing tools, expertise, and frameworks to strengthen Open Science capabilities and meet the evolving needs of researchers and organisations.

The **OSTrails training targets a broad audience**, including various communities from research infrastructures and institutions, with different levels of performance and responsibility, from researchers, research managers and project officers, to data stewards, data librarians and repository managers, including policy makers. Furthermore, OSTrails' target audience benefits from its engagement strategy, which is supported by communication and dissemination efforts. While these activities do not primarily focus on training, they play a crucial role in fostering involvement in the project's processes and outcomes, enhancing stakeholder participation and impact.

To complement the core of the training activities, established within this roadmap, OSTrails will offer and curate a training library featuring tutorials, guides, lesson plans, and case studies. In addition, for accessibility and scalability, OSTrails will utilise existing e-learning platforms, including OpenAIRE’s OpenPlato and INRIA’s ePoc mobile application. A strong emphasis will be placed on developing reusable learning resources and toolkits, ensuring their accessibility through open repositories, therefore all learning

³ FAIR Implementation Framework: <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

resources will be made openly available and onboarded in the EOSC EU-node training resource catalogue, ensuring broad accessibility and long-term impact.

This report details the strategic approach, implementation plan, and expected outcomes of the training roadmap, highlighting the role of structured training activities in fostering a sustainable and interconnected research ecosystem.

This deliverable is structured in five chapters, with the first being the introduction, and with four main parts detailing the planned training roadmap activities. Chapter 2 describes the training roadmap and lists all training activities and learning resources to be developed along with their purpose, target audience, learning objectives, timeline and milestones. Chapter 3 presents the training platforms, tools and methodologies used to support the delivery of training activities and learning resources. Chapter 4 outlines and clarifies the concept of an integrated competence centre. Lastly, Chapter 5 contains the training timeline and offers a comprehensive overview of key actions and scheduled delivery dates for each training activity and learning resource outlined in the training roadmap.

2. Training roadmap

The training roadmap details essential initiatives and resources that will be developed to fulfil OSTrails' training goals. This roadmap includes a training library, learning resources, guidance toolkits, online courses, train-the-trainer bootcamps, a mentorship program, and a trainer network and directory. This chapter is organised by training activities and learning resources, detailing their purpose, target audience, learning objectives, timeline, and milestones.

The new learning resources will follow the FAIR-by-Design methodology⁴ to support the production of learning resources following the FAIR principles. Thus, ensuring the use of standardised metadata schema to describe learning resources, the use of common apps and file formats when creating the resources, making them available in open repositories, ensuring their reusability and reproducibility, among other actions that will be followed as described in chapter 3.6. The main results from the activities planned on this roadmap will be aggregated in the “Training Corner” page of the OSTrails portal at

⁴ Filiposka, Sonja, Green, Dominique, Mishev, Anastas, Kjorveziroski, Vojdan, Corleto, Andrea, Napolitano, Eleonora, Paolini, Gabriela, Di Giorgio, Sara, Janik, Joanna, Schirru, Luca, Gingold, Arnaud, Hadrossek, Christine, Souyiultzoglou, Irakleitos, Leister, Carolin, & Lazzeri, Emma. (2023). *Skills4EOSC D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Learning Materials* (GitBook). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8305539>; https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/FAIR-by-Design_Book/;

Filiposka, S., Green, D., Mishev, A., Kjorveziroski, V., Corleto, A., Napolitano, E., Paolini, G., Di Giorgio, S., Janik, J., Schirru, L., Gingold, A., Hadrossek, C., Souyiultzoglou, I., Leister, C., & Pavone, G. (2025). *FAIR-by-Design Methodology for learning materials*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14711525>

<https://ostrails.eu/training>. This page serves as an entry point for the learning resources, online courses, among other resources produced within the project to train professionals of research institutions, funders, and RIs, and enable those specialists and researchers to boost knowledge, reuse support materials and be inspired by other experts to develop new skills.

2.1. Training library

2.1.1. Purpose

Several initiatives, projects and institutions have been developing learning and support materials covering topics on research data management and planning, monitoring and assessment of research results, so that the creation of a training library based on existing resources and relevant to the OSTrails activities, will contribute to offer to an easy way to discover and access learning and support resources by its stakeholders.

The main aim of this task is to deliver a training library with existing support/learning materials relevant to each of the three pillars of OSTrails, and targeted to specialists (managers of infrastructures, Open Science trainers, data stewards) trainers, and researchers. To this end, existing materials are being gathered and structured in a comprehensive and useful way, so that target users can discover them easily. These resources will be also relevant to support the development of the training programme and modules to be produced within the training roadmap activities.

First, a set of criteria were defined to clearly specify which learning resources should be selected, namely: the subjects should be related to the OSTrails pillars (Data Management Plans, Scientific Knowledge Graphs, FAIR Assessments), interoperability specifications, or services; the learning resource types should preferably be tutorials, guides, lesson plans and case studies.

Table 1. Criteria to select resources for the training library.

CRITERIA	DETAILS
Subjects	OSTrails pillars <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Management Plans • Scientific Knowledge Graphs • FAIR Assessments
Learning resource types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tutorials • Guides • Lesson plans • Case studies

Resources have been identified by all WP5 partners and collected in a spreadsheet. Each resource is described following a metadata profile previously defined by relevant initiatives⁵, with some additional fields relevant for the project activities.

Table 2. Training library metadata fields.

METADATA FIELDS	DESCRIPTION
Title	The human readable name of the learning resource.
Resource Authorship (Organisation / Authors)	The name of the entity(ies) authoring, managing or delivering the resource.
URL to resource	The URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable (e.g., Web Address URL, DOI, ARK, etc.).
OSTrails related pillars, interoperability specifications, or services	The name of the OSTrails pillar (DMP, SKG, FAIR Assessment), interoperability specifications or service for which this learning resource is referring to.
Learning Resource Type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource (Controlled vocabulary*).
Content resource type	The predominant content type of the learning resource (video, game, diagram, slides, etc.) (Controlled vocabulary*).
Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.
Keywords	The keyword(s) or tag(s) used to describe the resource.
License	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.
Version Date	The version date for the most recently published or broadcast resource.
Target Group	The principal users(s) for which the learning resource was designed.
Expertise Level	Target skill level in the topic being taught (Controlled vocabulary*).
Qualification	Identification of certification, accreditation or badge obtained with course or learning resource (Controlled vocabulary*).
Duration	Approximate or typical time (in hours) it takes to work with or through the learning resource for the typical intended target audience.

⁵ RDA Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources (https://www.rd-alliance.org/group_output/recommendations-for-a-minimal-metadata-set-to-aid-harmonised-discovery-of-learning-resources/); and EOSC Training Resource Profile Data Model (<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Training+Resource+Profile+-+Data+Model>)

Language	The language in which the resource was originally published or made available.
* A controlled vocabulary is specified in the spreadsheet used to collect the resources.	

After the resources collection, an evaluation will be carried out by the members of task 5.2 to select those that fulfil the specified criteria and OSTrails needs.

Once the evaluation of the first set of resources is complete, they will be published in the training library to be delivered on the Training Corner page of the OSTrails portal at <https://ostrails.eu/training>.

2.1.2. Target audience

This resource is designed for **managers of infrastructures, Open Science trainers, data stewards, and researchers**, equipping them with the knowledge, skills and useful resources to effectively manage, track and assess research data according to the OSTrails PTA framework⁶.

2.1.3. Objectives

The main objective of the Training Library is to provide a single discovery point of existing learning materials related to the three pillars of OSTrails and relevant to the adoption of good practices on research data management and planning, monitoring and assessment of research results, as well as to guide the use of tools and services to be delivered by the OSTrails technical work packages.

The Training Library will include not only existing materials produced by other initiatives and partners, but also the resources that will be produced as part of the project's activities as described in this deliverable.

2.1.4. Timeline and milestones

Table 3. Timeline and milestones for the training library.

ACTIVITY	DEADLINE
Specification of selection criteria	M7-8 (Aug. - Sep. 2024)

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/13145788>

Specification of metadata fields to describe resources	M7-8 (Aug. - Sep. 2024)
Build and deliver the tool to collect resources	M8 (Sep. 2024)
Collection of resources	M9-36 (Oct. 2024 - Jan. 2027)
Evaluation of resources	M9-36 (Oct. 2024 - Jan. 2027)
Delivery of the Training Library	M12-36 (Jan. 2025 - Jan. 2027)
Update the Training Library with new resources	M13-36 Feb.2025 - Jan. 2027)

Table 4. KPIs and metrics for the training library.

KPIs	METRICS
# resources listed in the Training library	~30 /year (90 overall)

2.2. Learning resources and guidance

toolkits

2.2.1. Purpose

With the aim of providing an organised set of learning resources to support the adoption of OSTrails interoperability specifications and services (see D1.4 OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture), three guidance toolkits will be delivered, aligned with each of the OSTrails pillars (Scientific Knowledge Graphs, FAIR Assessments, and Data Management Plans). This activity will be aligned with the OSTrails Commons being developed as part of the activities of WP2 and specified in the Deliverable 2.5 OSTrails Commons Specifications.

The OSTrails Commons are organised into five key components, ensuring comprehensive coverage of all included resources:

- Data Management Plan (DMP) Platforms - DMP Commons
- Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) - SKG Commons
- FAIR Assessment Tools - FAIR Commons
- Cross-Cutting and Supporting Resources
- Management and Governance

These guidance toolkits will include resources from the webinars, workshops and hackathons organised within the project activities, as well as the new how-to guides, factsheets and tutorials that will be produced in line with the developments from the technical work packages (WP1, WP2, WP3).

Target users will find the relevant learning resources organised by each pillar, facilitating the support provided to users in the context in which they are developing their activities, whether in the context of Scientific Knowledge Graphs, FAIR Assessments, or Data Management Plans. Guidance toolkits will be published once the OSTrails interoperability specifications and services are available, and the initial learning resources related to them have been produced. The toolkits will be continuously updated as new services and materials become available.

Regarding learning resources, distinct types will be created – how-to guides, factsheets and tutorials – so that target users can find the most appropriate support according to their needs and stage of development in adopting the OSTrails Commons. These resources will be developed jointly between the training team and the partners from technical work packages, including the contributions from technical deliverables and their respective publication dates (see Annex I).

The delivery of these learning resources will be made available in distinct platforms. The guidance toolkits will be delivered in a dedicated section of the Training Corner page on the OSTrails website at <https://ostrails.eu/training>, and the learning resources will be published in the OSTrails community on the Zenodo repository at <https://zenodo.org/communities/ostrails> (how-to guides and factsheets) and in the YouTube OSTrails channel (tutorials, webinar recordings).

The following table outlines the content structure of each learning resource type, along with the main topics covered.

Table 5. Learning resource types, structure and topics.

LEARNING RESOURCE TYPE	STRUCTURE / GOAL	FORMAT/DELIVERY MODE	TOPICS
Guidance toolkits	List of learning resources organised by OSTrails pillar. A single-entry point of learning resources to support the adoption of the OSTrails interoperability specifications and services.	OSTrails Web page (linked in the Training corner)	Data Management Plans; Scientific Knowledge Graphs; FAIR Assessments.
How-to guides	Structured and targeted information on how to use the OSTrails software and services. Structure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What it is • What it does • Getting started • How can I use it • Technical Requirements • Support 	OSTrails Web page (linked in the Training corner); PDF document to be published on Zenodo.	How to use OSTrails software and services.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Information 		
Factsheets	A two-page document containing the essential information to have an overview on the topic. To be used in dissemination activities.	PDF document to be published on Zenodo.	OSTrails pillars (DMPs, SKGs, FAIR Assessments); OSTrails reference architecture and interoperability frameworks.
Tutorials	Short video tutorials with instructions on how to use the OSTrails software and services.	Videos to be published on YouTube and embedded in how-to guides and online courses.	How to use software and services.

2.2.2. Target audience

Researchers, Data stewards, Data librarians, Research managers, Infrastructure developers and operators, Repository managers and Publishers, Trainers of RDM / Open Science, Research executives, Funders, Science policy makers.

2.2.3. Learning objectives

The toolkits will be organised according to the project pillars and aligned with the Deliverable D1.4 in which the OSTrails reference architecture is introduced along with three Interoperability Frameworks aligned with the project's pillars, as well as with the structure of OSTrails Commons as specified in the Deliverable D2.5.

The structure of the Commons is designed to provide a clear and scalable framework that organises the various resources supporting interoperability. These resources are composed of multiple core components based on the Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) Framework. The structure includes layers of components that further define the types of resources available and their intended uses, ranging from technical specifications and data models to documentation and APIs.

Regarding learning resources, they will cover distinct learning objectives as follows.

Guidance toolkits:

- Familiarise with the OSTrails reference architecture and interoperability frameworks.

- Understand the OSTrails pillars (Scientific Knowledge Graphs, FAIR Assessments, and Data Management Plans).
- Get to know the OSTrails software and services, along with the requirements for their use.
- Prepare for and carry out the integration of the OSTrails software and services.

How-to guides:

- Understand the purpose and benefits of each OSTrails software and services.
- Perform the use of OSTrails software and services.

Factsheets:

- Familiarise with the OSTrails reference architecture and interoperability frameworks.
- Understand the OSTrails pillars (Scientific Knowledge Graphs, FAIR Assessments, and Data Management Plans).

Tutorials:

- Understand how to use the OSTrails software and services.

2.2.4. Timeline and milestones

Table 6. Preliminary timeline and milestones of learning resources and guidance toolkits.

ACTIVITY	DEADLINE
Guidance toolkit: Scientific Knowledge Graphs	M17 – M35 (June 2025 – December 2026)
Guidance toolkit: FAIR Assessments	M17 – M35 (June 2025 – December 2026)
Guidance toolkit: Data Management Plans	M17 – M35 (June 2025 – December 2026)
How-to guides on how to use OSTrails software and services	M16 – M35 (May 2025 – December 2026)
Factsheets on the OSTrails pillars	M15 – M17 (April – June 2025)
Factsheets on the OSTrails reference architecture and interoperability frameworks	M15 – M17 (April – June 2025)
Tutorials on how to use software and services	M16 - M35 (May 2025 – December 2026)

Table 7. KPIs and metrics of learning resources and guidance toolkits.

KPIs	METRICS
# guidance toolkits	3
# downloads of learning resources	1000

2.3. Online courses

2.3.1. Purpose

Courses will be developed to educate pilot participants and external stakeholders on the benefits of adopting the OSTrails Interoperability Specifications, on how to use the services developed within technical work packages (WP1, WP2, WP3) and introductory modules on maDMPs, SKGs and FAIR Assessment. These courses will follow the self-paced learning approach and will be hosted in the Learning Management System OpenPlato (<https://openplato.eu/>) and in the Mobile Learning Platform ePoc (<https://epoc.inria.fr/en/>).

The use of both platforms aims to have distinct approaches to content delivery and to improve the learner's experience. On the one hand, the courses delivered on OpenPlato will have more structured and complete content and, on another hand, learning modules delivered on ePoc will be designed for rapid learning with focused, synthetic and short learning content to complement OpenPlato courses and training sessions (bootcamps, workshops).

Table 8. Platforms to deliver online courses.

PLATFORM	APPROACH
OpenPlato	Self-paced courses to introduce learners to the main OSTrails topics, to offer in-depth content on how to adopt best practices on interoperability specifications, and how to use software and services.
ePoc	Self-paced learning modules to be considered as a complement to OpenPlato courses, bootcamps, or workshops.

Two courses will be developed, the first focused on Data Management Plans (DMPs) and machine actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs), and the second focused on how to use the software and services developed by the technical work packages (WP1, WP2, WP3).

OpenPlato and ePoc content will be designed jointly to provide relevant and complementary learning modalities, objectives, outcomes and assessments.

Courses topics:

- Data Management Plans and maDMPs, to include modules on:
 - Introduction to the OSTrails pillars.
 - Introduction to Open Science and research data lifecycle
 - Introduction to DMPs and maDMPs.
 - Software and services to support the creation and publication of maDMPs;
 - Introduction to the OSTrails reference architecture and the Interoperability Framework.
- How to use the OSTrails software and services, to include modules on:
 - Introduction to the OSTrails pillars.
 - OSTrails reference architecture and interoperability framework
 - DMP Interoperability Framework.
 - SKG Interoperability Framework.
 - FAIR Testing Interoperability Framework.
 - Software and services developed within OSTrails.
 - Requirements to use OSTrails software and services.

For each course an evaluation quiz will be created, so the learners can evaluate their knowledge acquisition and get a certificate of completion, by fulfilling the evaluation criteria. Both platforms, OpenPlato and ePoc, will have the certificate of completion, which will be awarded to learners completing successfully the course. To successfully complete the course, the learner must read all the content and obtain a minimum score of 80% in the evaluation quiz.

The development of the courses and their respective modules will rely on collaboration with the project's technical partners (mainly with the WP leaders), who will assist in the development of content on how to use the software and services, as well as with the project's pilots who will identify training needs.

The details of the content and learning objectives, including the learning needs of the target audience, will be defined iteratively in specific meetings throughout 2025, in compliance with the defined plan.

The courses will initially be delivered as a pilot for testing and evaluation, and after this validation process a final version will be produced.

2.3.2. Target audience

Course “Data Management Plans and maDMPs” (1st):

- Researchers, Specialists (managers of infrastructures, Open Science trainers, Data stewards).

Course “How to use the OSTrails software and services” (2nd):

- Specialists (managers of infrastructures, Open Science trainers, Data stewards).

2.3.3. Learning objectives

Here is a proposed set of learning objectives which the course developers can further refine depending on the learning needs of the targeted audience (to be updated, if needed, based on the iterative process of specific meetings throughout the year 2025).

Course (1st): Data Management Plans and maDMPs.

- Explain the components of a DMP and its relevance to support the research life cycle.
- Explain what is a maDMP and know how to benefit from the exchange of information across research tools and systems.
- Apply the best practices in preparing for a DMP.
- Use the tools to create a DMP.
- Describe with the OSTrails reference architecture and the Interoperability Framework.

Course (2nd): How to use the OSTrails software and services.

- Describe the OSTrails reference architecture.
- Describe the Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF), the relation to key elements, and applications in OSTrails.
- Describe the FAIR Testing Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF), its sub-components and standards.
- Describe the DMP Interoperability Framework (DMP-IF) and its key elements.
- Use the software and services for each OSTrails pillar.
- Implement the requirements to use the OSTrails software and services.
- Execute the integration of OSTrails software and services.
- Use the OSTrails software and services.

2.3.4. Timeline and milestones

Table 9. Preliminary timeline and milestones for the online courses.

ACTIVITY	DEADLINE
Training analysis for the 1 st course (goals, learning outcomes)	M16 (May 2025)
1 st course delivery (pilot)	M21 (October 2025)
1 st course delivery (final version)	M24 (January 2026)
Training analysis for the 2 nd course (goals, learning outcomes)	M25 (February 2026)
2 nd course delivery (pilot)	M28 (May 2026)
2 nd course delivery (final version)	M32 (September 2026)

Table 10. KPIs and metrics for the online courses.

KPIs	METRICS
# courses	2
# course modules	6
# learners	> 150

2.4. Train-the-trainer Bootcamps

2.4.1. Purpose

The qualification of trainers in the core topics of OSTrails is essential to reach a broader number of users trained to adopt the OSTrails specifications and services. For that reason, two train-the-trainer bootcamps will be organised to provide learning resources and training tutorials on the OSTrails pillars, namely on Data Management Plans, Scientific Knowledge Graphs and FAIR Assessment, aimed to train specialists and establish networks of trainers.

Bootcamps will be organised within relevant physical and online workshops and conferences, taking into consideration the national and thematic pilots' agendas. The events to be considered for co-allocating the organisation of bootcamps are identified below:

- RDA plenary meetings (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/>)

- LDK - Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (<http://2025.ldk-conf.org>)
- EUDAT Summer School / Conference
- Open Science FAIR, 15-17 September 2025, Cern, Switzerland
- International Digital Curation Conference
- OpenAIRE General Assemblies
- Open Repositories Conference

The train-the-trainer bootcamps will be delivered in OpenPlato platform at <https://openplato.eu/>, where participants will be able to access content and interact with teachers.

2.4.2. Target audience

Target users: trainers from the **OSTrails pilots (national and thematic)**, and from **National Infrastructures and Research Infrastructures** (recruited from relevant competence centres and training initiatives of the European Research Area and ESFRI RIs, utilising the stakeholder network of the project partners involved in the case study pilots).

2.4.3. Learning objectives

At the end of the train-the-trainer bootcamp, trainers will be able to:

- Plan and run a training session on the OSTrails specifications and services.
- Explain the OSTrails pillars (Data Management Plans, Scientific Knowledge Graphs and FAIR Assessment);
- Explain the OSTrails reference architecture and Interoperability Frameworks.
- Explain the requirements to use the OSTrails software and services.
- Demonstrate and explain the use of the OSTrails services.

2.4.4. Timeline and milestones

Table 11. Preliminary timeline and milestones for the train-the-trainer bootcamps.

ACTIVITY	DEADLINE
Training analysis for the 1 st bootcamp (main topics, learning outcomes, target users)	M15 (April 2025)
1 st bootcamp	2 nd semester of 2025
Training analysis for the 2 nd bootcamp (main topics, learning outcomes, target users)	M27 (April 2026)
2 nd bootcamp	2 nd semester of 2026

Note: the dates will be identified according to the events to be defined.

Table 12. KPIs and metrics for the train-the-trainer bootcamps.

KPIs	METRICS
# bootcamps	2
# participants in each bootcamp	25-35 (15 National Infrastructures, 15 Research Infrastructures)

2.5. Mentorship programme

2.5.1. Purpose

The OSTrails consortium brings together senior experts in Data Management Plans, Scientific Knowledge Graphs, and FAIR Assessment. This represents an excellent opportunity to create a structured initiative for sharing their expertise and knowledge with peers. Therefore, a mentorship program will be organised aiming to promote learning and developing skills in the main project topics, through personalised guidance, support, and the sharing of experiences.

The mentorship program is targeted to IT infrastructures managers, research support staff and funders' support staff, who will have the opportunity to receive mentorship from senior experts from the OSTrails consortium.

Mentors will be selected from the OSTrails consortium according to their expertise in the main project topics namely Data Management Plans, Scientific Knowledge Graphs and FAIR Assessment, and considering training experience.

Participants will be recruited from relevant competence centres and training initiatives of the European Research Area and ESFRI RIs, using the stakeholder network of the project partners involved in the pilot case studies.

Main features of the program:

- Duration: 1 year
- Meetings frequency: every month, between experts (mentors) and participants (mentees)
- Type of sessions:
 - One-to-one meeting.
 - 1 mentor for a team of 3-4 participants (combine similar participants needs).

2.5.2. Target audience

Target users: IT infrastructure managers, Research support staff, Funders' support officers (recruited from relevant competence centres and training initiatives of the European Research Area and ESFRI RIs, utilising the stakeholder network of the project partners involved in the case study pilots).

2.5.3. Learning objectives

By participating in the mentorship programme, participants will:

- Improve specific technical or soft skills in the targeted topic (DMP, SKG, or FAIR assessment).
- Learn about best practices, and insights from the expert's experience.
- Develop the ability to adopt best practices and to implement the OSTrails services and specifications.
- Expand their professional network.

2.5.4. Timeline and milestones

Table 13. Preliminary timeline and milestones for the mentorship programme.

ACTIVITY	DEADLINE
Mentorship programme plan (including the list of mentors and the announcement, participants selection criteria)	M13 (February 2025)
Announcement and open call for mentees	M14 (March 2025)
Participants (mentees) selection	M15 (April 2025)
Develop a matching process: criteria definition for pairing mentors and mentees.	M16 (May 2025)
Kick-off session with all mentees and mentors	M17 (June 2025)
Mentorship programme	M17-M28 (June 2025 – May 2026)

Table 14. KPIs and metrics for the mentorship programme

KPIs	METRICS
# mentorship programme	1
# participants / mentees	> 40

2.6. Network and directory of trainers

2.6.1. Purpose

Promote the creation of directory and network of trainers who can establish a link with OSTrails pilot activities, and the competence centres of the national and research communities being developed in the context of Skills4EOSC project and other relevant training initiatives within the context of EOSC.

During the implementation of the project activities, we plan to create a directory of trainers that will support the ongoing training activities and that will result in training activities, namely bootcamps.

This activity will only be relevant in the context of the OSTrails project and is not intended to continue beyond its duration, as the identified trainers will be included in networks of national initiatives and research infrastructures, and will be a relevant contribution for established networks, such as:

- SSH Trainers Directory: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/trainers-directory>.
- CLARIN trainers' network: <https://www.clarin.eu/trainers-network>.
- ELIXIR RDM Trainer Network: <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management/trainer-network>.
- SKILLS4EOSC user support network: <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network/user-support-network>.
- OpenAIRE trainers - <https://openplato.eu/>.
- FORRT: <https://forrt.org/>.

The network and directory of trainers will be delivered in a dedicated section of the Training Corner page in the OSTrails website at <https://ostrails.eu/training>.

2.6.2. Timeline and milestones

Table 15. Preliminary timeline and milestones for the network and directory of trainers.

ACTIVITY	DEADLINE
Create and deliver the directory on the website	M17 (June 2025)
Populate the directory with trainers' profiles from bootcamps and members of pilot partners	M17-M32 (June 2025 – Sept. 2026)

Table 16. KPIs and metrics for the network and directory of trainers.

KPIs	METRICS
# trainers listed	50

3. Training platforms, tools and methodologies

The OSTrails training roadmap includes several initiatives whose development and planning require the use of existing tools and methodologies. This chapter identifies and describes the tools to be used, as well as the methodologies adopted for creating learning resources.

The **online courses** will be developed in distinct steps, starting with the training analysis, in which the objectives and learning outcomes are defined, followed by the content production to prepare the first version of the course that will be piloted, taking to the next stage, where the courses will be piloted by OSTrails pilot partners. On this step, learners will be invited to do the course, for testing and evaluating it, so we can receive valuable contributions to update and improve the course. After this validation process, the course will be updated with these contributions, to prepare the final version of the course.

ePoc modules are designed for rapid learning with focused, synthetic and short learning content to reinforce the learning experience during OpenPlato courses, live training sessions (bootcamps, workshops) and at any time on the learner's mobile device. They will address learning objectives dedicated to OSTrails related concepts and tools, and to Open Science more generally (especially DMP, maDMP and metadata for interoperability).

3.1. OpenPlato – learning management system

The online courses and train-the-train bootcamps planned to be developed as described both in the Online courses and Train-the-trainer Bootcamps chapters, will be delivered in the OpenPlato platform (www.openplato.eu), a Learning Management System (LMS) operated by OpenAIRE to host training resources for Open Science related topics.

OpenPlato, based on Moodle software (<https://moodle.com/>), includes the common LMS functionalities to create and manage learning resources and certifications (badges for the conclusion of learning paths and certificates for courses). It also includes a catalogue feature, a dedicated environment to create spaces in multilingual formats which can be based on a country or on specific themes or projects and can be used for navigation or to group similar content.

3.2. ePoc – rapid learning mobile app

ePoc (Electronic Pocket Open Course) <https://epoc.inria.fr/> is a completely free and open-source mobile app. The ePoc app is designed for rapid learning using rich and varied common learning materials (text, video, podcast, infographics, interactive activities or quizzes) for easy reference anytime outside the online course.

It is specifically designed to:

- introduce basic notions or upgrade knowledge on advanced specific concept.
- consolidate and reinforce acquired skill.
- summarize key learning points.
- foster engagement with additional learning content.

In addition, ePoc modules:

- can be accessed and downloaded to a mobile phone using a QR code, without the need for an ePoc user account.
- are available at any time on a learner's mobile device without the need for an Internet connection once downloaded.
- could be integrated into the OpenPlato LMS via a SCORM package, subject to technical compliance verification.

3.3. Articulate and ePoc editor – authoring tools

The online courses will be composed of distinct content resource types, such as video, image, text, and slides, among others. They will be produced using various content production tools, from the simplest, such as a screen recording tool for producing video tutorials, to more complex tools, such as an authoring tool to create content.

Authoring tools, with their diverse functionalities and development options, add significant value to learning resources, by leveraging different types of multimedia content and various levels of interactivity. An authoring tool often includes storyboarding and editing features that enable creating and combining different elements within an online course (text, video, audio, graphics, and animations).

The main authoring tools used to produce content will be Articulate 360 (<https://www.articulate.com/360/>) and ePoc editor (<https://epoc.inria.fr/en/editor/>).

The authoring tool Articulate 360 will be used to produce the content for the online courses, which will be made available on the OpenPlato platform. Articulate is a tool that allows the creation of rich and dynamic contents, the creation of interactive quizzes, among other functionalities. Contents are published in open format SCORM.

The ePoc editor authoring tool is a web-based desktop application to design, build, publish and share a mobile-first learning content in ePoc Open file or SCORM formats. As for ePoc app, ePoc editor is a free and open-source software.

The ePoc editor will be used to produce ePoc modules, on the one hand in Moodle-SCORM format for integration into online courses if technical compliance is confirmed, and on another hand in ePoc format for access during training sessions and at any time during and outside the training program.

By developing, maintaining and offering ePoc and ePoc Editor software for mobile learning, Inria's policy is to promote a free, easy and open access to knowledge, as well as the ability to produce this knowledge, while ensuring respect for privacy. ePoc source code is available on <https://gitlab.inria.fr/learninglab/epoc>.

3.4. Overview of platforms and tools

Table 17. Overview of platforms and tools used to deliver learning resources and training activities.

PLATFORM AND TOOLS	LEARNING RESOURCES / TRAINING ACTIVITY
OpenPlato	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of online courses • Delivery of train-the-trainer bootcamps
ePoc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of mobile learning modules
Articulate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of the online course's contents to be delivered in OpenPlato
ePoc editor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of mobile-first learning content (to be delivered on the ePoc mobile app)
OSTrails website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of training library • Links to the learning resources and training activities • Network and directory of trainers
Zenodo repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of how-to guides and factsheets
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of tutorials

3.5. FAIR-by-Design implementation

The production of learning resources will follow the FAIR-by-Design Methodology (https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/FAIR-by-Design_Book/), to ensure the FAIRness of the produced materials. Following this methodology and its main development stages (<https://www.skills4eosc.eu/resources/fair-by-design-methodology>) will help guide on creating learning materials that are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

The following table showcases the implementation of the FAIR-by-Design Methodology in practice, namely the actions we will ensure for each development stage.

Table 18. FAIR-by-Design implementation to produce learning resources

FAIR-BY-DESIGN STAGE	IMPLEMENTATION IN OSTRAILS
Stage 1 – Prepare Adopt a metadata schema	Learning materials will be described following a metadata profile previously defined by relevant initiatives (RDA minimal metadata set for learning resources and EOSC Training Resource Profile Data Model).
Stage 2 – Discover Reuse materials	Deliver a training library with existing support/learning materials relevant to each of the three pillars of OSTrails.

Stage 3 – Design Build a concept map of learning materials	Training roadmap specifying the purpose, target audience and learning objectives.
Stage 4 – Produce Use of common apps and file formats	Apps/Tools: Articulate, Moodle, ePoc, ePoc editor. Formats: SCORM, ePoc (Zip packaged with Text and JSON based standards).
Stage 5 – Publish Release of the produced learning materials and their metadata	Deliver the online courses in OpenPlato (Moodle LMS platform) and ePoc. Deposit learning resources on Zenodo. Register learning resources in the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub, accompanied with metadata following the RDA minimal metadata set for learning resources.
Stage 6 – Verify Quality Assurance and FAIR verification	Use the FAIR-by-Design methodology Quality Assurance checklist to check the FAIRness of produced learning materials.
Stage 7 - Continuous Improvement Collect feedback and improve	Conduct a satisfaction and monitoring assessment.

3.6. Satisfaction and monitoring assessment

The support materials to be produced will follow a set of criteria as mentioned above, not only to meet the requirements of the project activities, but also to meet the needs of the target users (learners). From the point of view of meeting the learners' needs, it is essential to evaluate their satisfaction and the utility of the training activities that will be provided. Therefore, mechanisms for evaluating and monitoring training activities will be developed, including satisfaction assessment surveys and usage monitoring.

For satisfaction assessment, a survey will be conducted that includes questions about the clarity of learning objectives, quality and utility of the learning resources and training activities.

Regarding monitoring, a set of usage data will be collected from the platforms where the learning resources and training activities will be delivered. The measurement will include views and downloads, participants, among others as detailed in table below.

Platforms where resources and training activities will be delivered offer monitoring tools which will facilitate collection of usage data.

In addition to usage statistics, OpenPlato also issues certificates of completion, which measure the number of students who have successfully completed online courses and bootcamps, as well as providing students with a document certifying that they have successfully completed the training activity.

Regarding ePoc, each specific module certification will be issued on the ePoc app. It could also be transferred to the OpenPlato platform using an LTI/xAPI plugin and user authentication after validating the user’s consent (technical feasibility of this functionality will need to be verified). Statistics and learning data from ePoc OSTrails, such as the number of downloads, pages viewed, certificates issued, videos viewed or questions answered, will be accessible.

An overview of all metrics to be considered through platforms is listed in the table below.

Table 19. Overview of metrics for the satisfaction and monitoring assessment.

TRAINING ACTIVITY	METRICS
Training Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # learning resources collected • # page views
Learning resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # produced how-to guides, factsheets and tutorials • # views and downloads of how-to guides, factsheets and tutorials
Guidance toolkits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # page views
Online courses and ePoc modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # enrolled students • # students completing successfully the course
Train-the-trainer Bootcamps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # participants
Mentorship programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # mentors and participants • # sessions between mentors and participants
Network and directory of trainers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # trainers • # page views

4. Supporting integrated competence centre

OSTrails supports the development and enhancement of competence centres at European, national, and infrastructure levels by fostering collaboration, best practice sharing, and alignment with EOSC training and skills related initiatives, like Skills4EOSC and OSCARS, including the EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group (OA5) on Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling.

While OSTrails project does not aim the establishment of a competence centre itself, it serves as a key enabler, providing tools, expertise, and frameworks to strengthen Open Science and FAIR data capabilities and meet the evolving needs of researchers, research support staff and infrastructure providers.

Figure 2. OSTrails Competence Centres supporting mechanism.

Through this integrated approach - where training initiatives directly support pilot partners and a broader community via bootcamps, mentorship programs, and courses - OSTrails underscores the importance of equipping competence centres with professional expertise, services, and tools.

Depending on the structuring and development phase in which the competence centres are, whether at national level or at the thematic clusters level and also taking into account the establishment of the EOSC Nodes, OSTrails training and liaison teams will closely monitor the initiatives of EOSC where this process will be defined more clearly.

Despite being a work in progress, OSTrails will be well-positioned with the necessary conditions and planned actions to support competence centres through this integrated and complementary approach, training the professionals who can play a key role in their development.

5. Training timeline

Table 20. Integrated table with actions and timeline for each training activity.

	2024					2025												2026												2027
TRAINING ACTIVITIES / MONTHS	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	JAN.	FEB.	MAR.	APR.	MAY	JUN.	JUL.	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	JAN.	FEB.	MAR.	APR.	MAY	JUN.	JUL.	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	JAN.
Training Library: specification of criteria and metadata fields																														
Training Library: Collection and evaluation of resources																														
Training Library delivery and update																														
Guidance toolkit: DMP																														
Guidance toolkit: SGK																														
Guidance toolkit: FAIR																														
How-to guides																														
Factsheets																														
Tutorials																														
Training analysis for the 1 st online course																														
1st course delivery (pilot)																														
1st course delivery (final version)																														
Training analysis for the 2 nd online course																														
2nd course delivery (pilot)																														
2nd course delivery (final version)																														
Training analysis for the 1st bootcamp																														
Bootcamp 1																														

TRAINING ACTIVITIES / MONTHS	2024					2025												2026											2027	
	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	JAN.	FEB.	MAR.	APR.	MAY	JUN.	JUL.	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	JAN.	FEB.	MAR.	APR.	MAY	JUN.	JUL.	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	JAN.
Training analysis for the 2nd bootcamp																														
Bootcamp 2																														
Mentorship programme (MP) plan																														
Announcement and open call for mentees (MP)																														
Mentee's selection (MP)																														
Matching process for pairing mentors and mentees (MP)																														
Kick-off session with all mentees and mentors (MP)																														
Mentorship programme																														
Create and deliver the directory of trainers available on the website																														
Populate the directory of trainers with profiles that result from bootcamps and members of pilot partners																														

Table 21. Summary of metrics and KPIs from the Training Roadmap.

ACTIVITIES	METRICS / KPIs
Training Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 90 resources
Learning resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 guidance toolkits • 1000 downloads of learning resources
Online courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 courses • 6 modules • > 150 learners
Train-the-trainer Bootcamps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 bootcamps • 25-35 participants (15 National Infrastructures, 15 Research Infrastructures)
Mentorship programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 mentorship programme • > 40 mentees
Network and directory of trainers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 trainers listed

Annexes

Annex I. Technical deliverables relevant to deliver learning resources

DELIVERABLE NO.	DELIVERABLE NAME	DUE DATE
D1.2	FAIRness Reference Model for Digital Objects V1	M12 (January 2025)
D1.3	FAIRness Reference Model for Digital Objects V2	M24 (January 2026)
D1.4	OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1	M12 (January 2025)
D1.5	OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V2	M30 (August 2026)
D2.2	OSTrails Software and Services V1	M14 (March 2025)
D2.3	OSTrails Software and Services V2	M24 (January 2026)
D2.4	OSTrails Software and Services V3	M32 (September 2026)
D3.1	DMP Evaluation Rubric and Service Specifications	M12 (January 2025)
D3.2	DMP Evaluation Service	M28 (May 2026)
D3.3	Toolbox of Testing Services	M30 (July 2026)
D3.4	Disciplinary and Thematic Community based Evaluation Extensions for Compliance Assessment V1	M18 (July 2025)
D3.5	Disciplinary and Thematic Community based Evaluation Extensions for Compliance Assessment V2	M30 (July 2026)
D3.6	SKG Research Product Quality toolbox	M34 (November 2026)